

Effectiveness of an Accomplished Extension Program in Digital Photography

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Abstract— This study evaluated the effectiveness of the accomplished extension program in digital photography conducted by the Technological University of the Philippines-College of Architecture and Fine Arts by determining its relevance, planning, implementation, resources, monitoring and evaluation. This also includes the benefits gained by the participants as part of the In-Service training program of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite. It utilized quantitative method of research using purposive sampling of the respondents (Junior and Senior High School Teachers) which attended the said training-workshop and this includes the officials of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite. Results revealed that the concluded extension program in digital photography (Skill, knowledge, advancement and livelihood) of the College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the Fine Arts department were very effective which indicated that the concluded extension program in digital photography were able to meet the set objectives. Moreover, the extension program in digital photography cater to the initial publication of the monthly journal of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite and division city schools winning in school paper competitions.

Keywords— *Digital Photography, Extension Program*

I. INTRODUCTION

Extension service is the process by which technology and innovation are transferred to an identified clientele with the ultimate objective of improving the delivery of instruction to the students by the junior and senior high school teachers. Extension services are also identified as one of the four fold functions of a higher education Institution. The Technological University of the Philippines specifically the Fine Arts department of the College of Architecture and Fine Arts, a government academic institution, is mandated to perform this function. The University Extension Service is directed to coordinate and operationalize the extension functions of the university and its campuses in accordance with the approved extension programs and priorities. One of the areas of services as provided by the University Extension Service is to package suitable and viable technologies for development and research results of the University, government and non-government organization for dissemination and adaptation, and utilization of the community.

According to Tanhueco-Tumapon (2018), that the pursuit of excellence by an institution, especially if it asserts excellence as a descriptor of its products and services, is an unending quest, Higher Education Institute's, with fervid

attempts, try to comply with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) memo orders to pursue the threefold function of higher education-research, instruction and community service (and as we academics know, weld them together). These are meant to make Philippine Higher Education Institute's stride along with Universities across borders recognized worldwide not only for the quality of their programs but, but as in corporate business, for their social initiatives as well.

Republic Act 7722, otherwise known as the Commission on Higher Education mandates institutions of higher learning like State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) to respond to the call for societal transformation. The aim is to serve the poorest of the poor, the less, the deprived and the oppressed (Elman, 1998).

Among SUCs most extension programs are demand driven and accreditation demand. Demand driven is community-based that encompasses basic functional needs and demands designed to establish and promote the general well-being of the teachers of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite. Trainings, seminars and workshops are requested by the officials of the said department upon identification of the specific needs of their teachers. On the other hand, the accreditation driven extension programs are implemented in responds to the requirements by an accrediting body and the implementation of the extension program in digital photography complements the curricular offering of the College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the Fine Arts department

The training-workshop in Digital Photography has been conducted by the College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the Fine Arts Department at the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite and accomplished last May 24, 25, 26 and 27, 2017 and participated by 108 junior and senior high school teachers coming from various school divisions of Bacoor City. The development of skills and knowledge in Digital Photography and Photojournalism are the objectives of the extension program conducted by the Technological University of the Philippines-College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the Fine Arts Department. The said extension program is a part of the In-Service training program of the Department of Education for the upgrading of the knowledge and skills of the junior and senior high school teachers. It substantiates that outstanding extension projects are recognized through measures such as importance, innovation, capacity of replication, sustainability, focus, scope, relevance and results,

number of publications and creative programs (Alcher, 2007). Furthermore, the extension programs conducted by the College of Architecture and Fine Arts is in coordination with the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite according to the nature of necessity of trainings for the junior and senior high school teachers.

The results of the study are of great bearing to the junior and senior high school teachers of Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite which can serve as basis policy formulation and enhancement of the extension programs and services of the Technological University of the Philippines-College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the Fine Arts department..

II. METHODS

The study employed the quantitative method of research and the researcher utilized the adopted instrument from the University Extension Service and the University Research and Development Service of the Technological University of the Philippines. The questionnaire is posted at the group site of the TLE/TVL facebook site of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite and retrieved after a month to validate and describe the effectiveness of the extension program of digital photography conducted at the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite.

The respondents are composed of 108 coming from the elementary, junior and senior high school teachers of the various school divisions, the TLE/TVL supervisor, Principals and Schools Division Superintendent.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extension service, as one of the four-fold functions of the university, endeavors to transfer technology and innovation to the elementary, junior and senior high school teachers to improve their living, develop the skills and knowledge in the latest technology in digital photography and expand the expertise in school paper layout. Therefore, extension programs and projects should be implemented properly to attain the set objectives.

Table 1 reveal that the extension program has provided additional knowledge and skills in shooting

photographs acquired a mean score of 4.46 and 4.67 for the ability and actual experience in handling digital cameras gaining a very effective rating. As for the knowledge in proper focusing of lenses in handling digital camera and accessories achieved a mean score of 4.40 while the appropriate training methods/approaches utilized during the training program gained a mean score of 4.78 receiving a very effective rating. Trainers-lecturers which provided the necessary knowledge and skills to the teachers obtain a mean score of 4.87 and the participants cooperation and attitude as well as adherence to

INDICATORS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Provided additional knowledge and skills in shooting photographs.	4.46	Very Effective
Ability and actual experience in handling digital cameras.	4.67	Very Effective
Knowledge in proper focusing of lenses in handling digital camera and Accessories.	4.40	Very Effective
Appropriate training methods/approaches is utilized during the conduct of the program.	4.78	Very Effective
Trainers-Lecturers provided the necessary knowledge and skills to the teachers.	4.87	Very Effective
Participants Cooperation and Attitude as well as adherence to the policies of the Extension Program.	4.24	Very Effective

the policies of the extension program achieved a mean score of 4.24 which is also very effective. These results signify that the extension program in digital photography of the College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the fine arts department have contributed to the advancement of the teachers of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite in developing the skills and knowledge in digital photography and it also reveals that the training-workshop in digital photography has achieved the goals and objectives of the extension program.

Table 1. Level of Effectiveness of the Extension Program Component in Digital Photography.

Table 2. Analysis of Variance on the Effectiveness of the Extension Program to the Teachers of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite as Perceived by the Respondents.

INDICATORS	IMPLEMENTER	DEPED OFFICIALS	TEACHERS/BENEFICIARIE	PROB.	INTERPRETATION
The training-workshop in digital photography helps the school divisions in developing their news publication.	4.31	4.20	4.28	0.254	Not Significant
Enhanced the knowledge and skills of the teachers to produce news publication of their schools.	4.34	4.46	4.10	0.271	Not Significant
Motivated the teachers to coach the students in school paper competitions.	4.49	4.31	4.48	0.620	Not Significant
Motivated to serve as an additional income to their livelihood the acquired knowledge and skills in digital photography	4.45	4.48	3.77	0.002	Significant
Motivated to produce the initial news publication of the Deped-Division of Bacoor City Cavite.	4.46	4.35	4.57	0.132	Not Significant
Helped the school divisions to be recognized in school paper competitions.	4.43	3.28	4.0	0.841	Not Significant

Table 2 indicates the significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the importance of the key factors of the extension program in digital photography. Prior to subsequent analysis of variance, normally test on the data was processed using Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z test. With p-value of 0.127, data were found to be normally distributed hence, the use of ANOVA was appropriate.

The data presents that among the all the key factors of the extension program in digital photography, motivation to serve as an additional income to their livelihood of the acquired knowledge and skills in digital photography is found to be critical and important for sustainability. This is apparent because the transfer of technology is intended for the additional livelihood of the teachers aside from the school paper layout recognitions and the overall goal of the program is clearly stated. The challenge to allocate more time for planning the extension program that can provide supplementary income for the teachers will be prioritize. Forest and Baker (1994) stated that the planning process offers opportunity to people who participate in it to learn, thus building leadership skills in the community that will likely contribute to self-help, independence and positive end results.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The College of Architecture and Fine Arts extension program in digital photography have generally facilitated in the development of the teacher’s development in producing news publication and recognitions acquired by schools’ division in school paper competitions. The extension services brought positive impacts such as: in enhancing the knowledge and skills of the teachers, thereby capacitating and empowering the teachers of Deped-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite which motivate to serve as additional income from their newly acquired knowledge and skills. The extension services of the College of Architecture and Fine Arts specifically the Fine Arts department provides the basis for the initial news publication of the Department of Education-Division of City Schools of Bacoor City Cavite and teachers are motivated to assists the students in developing the school paper publication of the schools division.

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